

SOME SOLUTIONS TO ENHANCE THE QUALITY OF SERVICES CONFERENCE CENTER IN HO CHI MINH CITY

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Abstract

In the current era of globalization, the development of services is an inevitable trend all over the world. In order to compete successfully in the economic industry, all countries, as well as businesses, must put a top priority on providing high-quality services to satisfy the increasing needs of customers and really consider service quality as a competitive advantage. Vietnam is increasingly opening the gate to welcome international friends to study, entertain, and do business, creating favorable conditions for our country's service industry to develop strongly. Convention and wedding centers have sprung up with a full range of material and technical facilities that can meet all the diverse and abundant needs of domestic and foreign guests. Customers are more and more interested in quality, especially in improving the service quality of various types of parties. Ho Chi Minh City is a densely populated place, the economic center of the country. Therefore, the business activities of conference services here are very diverse and rich, but fierce competition in the market. This requires businesses to always renew themselves by improving the quality of conference services to meet the increasing needs of customers and keep their place in the market while finding solutions. Overcome limited problems in the service provision process

Keywords: customer, conference, hospitality, solution, quality, economic

A. INTRODUCTION

Foodservice businesses, whether large or small, have challenges for many reasons. It requires businesses to have not only technical knowledge and skills but also business knowledge and people skills. The professional service style is one of the top selection factors of customers wishing to organize a party. Thanks to this factor, businesses will be able to expand and thrive and many job opportunities will be created. Therefore, service staff is an important component in the management apparatus because the success of the business depends greatly on them. The customers are not the ones who bring trouble to the business, they are the ones who pay for the business. Therefore, business enterprises must make customers feel that they are always warmly welcomed, respected, satisfied with requirements, and appreciated. Therefore, the service staff must have a professional attitude expressed through a smile and a neat and tidy appearance. In addition to the ability to serve professionally, the service staff must also know how to handle unexpected and unforeseen situations. Today, one of the most serious problems threatening the global catering industry is a growing labor shortage. The demand for qualified and professionally trained staff in this industry is immense. Besides, the competition between enterprises is getting fiercer. Due to the rapid development of society and technology, customers are more and more demanding in choosing food service establishments, food service business today is a very developing industry. Enterprises have easy access to market share but are also easily eliminated. Therefore, in order to survive and develop long-term in the catering industry, catering establishments, in general, need to promote their strengths and limit their

weaknesses. Service quality is the most important factor to help businesses retain old customers and increase many new customers.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

Initially, the concept of service quality was derived from the satisfaction of consumers with tangible products. But services are intangible, so it has made it very difficult for researchers to give a clear definition of the concept of service quality. For customers, tangible products are easy for them to evaluate with different products of different businesses. As for intangible products, it is not easy to evaluate, customers can only evaluate them after they have used them. Therefore, it can be said that service quality is very important in setting development goals and orientations for businesses in the future. In fact, the needs can change over time, so it is necessary to periodically review the quality requirements to be able to ensure that the products or services produced by the enterprise will best satisfy the needs of the customers. For consumers, needs are often translated into characteristics with certain standards. Meeting tourism, often referred to as conferences, congresses, courses, or Exhibitions – trade fairs and expositions, regards journeys made by company employees and other people as part of their job Berbeka, Borodako, Klimek, Niemczyk, & Seweryn, (2010). Thus, it is a highly diversified segment of tourism, which makes it difficult to formulate a generally accepted definition Davidson & Cope (2003). Practically, business tourism consists of the following: 1) convention tourism, including five types of meetings: congress, conference, convention, symposium, and seminar; 2) trainings and courses held outside the permanent place of residence, which belong to the category of business and work-related trips; 3) convention events, combined with fairs and exhibitions; and 4) incentive trips. Business travel usually takes place outside the tourist season; sometimes, trips last several days and are of great economic importance, because they involve larger expenses than other forms of tourism. They also require comprehensive service as regards the organization of the event, the journey, stay, entertainment, etc. This means the involvement of numerous specialized firms professional business travel providers, conference and congress organizers, etc. Business trips are also of considerable social significance, creating an opportunity to exchange information, knowledge, and experience during meetings and scientific, professional, political, or religious assemblies. All of this contributes to the popularisation of economic, social, and cultural innovations Davidson & Cope, (2003).

C. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research explores the factors affecting customer satisfaction to purchase and consume conference services. Qualitative research was conducted through exchange interviews with the banquet department of the center. For research to be valid with reality. In order for the interview to go smoothly and without wasting time, the research prepared questions to get opinions of the interviewees. After the interview ended, synthesize comments and proceed to build a research model including five factors or variables affecting customer satisfaction when using services at the Convention Center. The five suggested variables include: (1) facilities, (2) food quality, (3) hygiene, (4) staff, (5) service. Quantitative research is through sample design, samples are collected through questionnaires surveyed by customers. In addition, observe and

record, and gather past data. The purpose of this method is to measure and test the relationship between variables in the form of metrics and statistics. Testing the scale and the suitability of the figure by SPSS 20 software, in order to assess the importance of variables affecting quantitative research. The obtained data will be encrypted and processed using SPSS 20 software the sample size must collect the necessary information for the study to reach certain reliability. Estimate the sample size according to the formula: $n \geq 8m + 50$ Hoang Trong and Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc, (2005). This study was conducted to survey the minimum sample size of 300. The survey questionnaire was sent to interviews, then data was collected and processed using SPSS 20.0 software. Each question is designed to represent a criterion for assessing customer satisfaction. The questionnaire consists of 25 questions corresponding to 5 variables affecting customer satisfaction.

D. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In terms of gender, the number of male customers accounted for 52.3% more than the number of female customers accounted for only 47.7%. Thus, the number of male customers attending the conference was many female customers. Next, the number of customers who are housewives accounts for the highest rate of 49%, followed by the number of guests who are workers and officials, accounting for 22.3%, the number of guests who are self-employed accounted for 18.7%, followed by the number of students who are students, accounting for 6.3%.

Table 1. The number of male and female customers

Targets		Quantity	(%)
Sex	Male	157	52.3
	Female	143	47.7
Age	From 16 – 25 years old	25	8,3
	From 26 đến 39 years old	65	21,7
	From 40 đến 50 years old	143	47,7
	Over 51 years old	67	22.3
Occupation	Student	19	6.3
	Self-employed	56	18.7
	Housewives	147	49
	Workers	67	22.3
Total		300	100,0

The number of guests at the conference party is housewives. They have a need to exchange, meet, and gossip because housewives often have a lot of free time. The number of conferences between the ages of 40 and 50 accounted for the highest proportion of 47.7%, followed by those aged 51 and older accounting for 22.3 %, the age group from 26 to 39 accounted for 21.7% and the lowest rate was from 16 to 25 years old, accounting for 8.3%. Visitors to the conference are mainly in the age group of 40 to 50 years old. This is a group of guests with money and status, they have enough knowledge and skills to assess the satisfaction of the center's party service quality.

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha reliability test results and KMO

Factor	Number of variables observe	Cronbach's Alpha	Conclusion
Facilities	5	0.823	Qualified
Food quality	5	0.889	Qualified
Hygiene	5	0.929	Qualified
Staff	5	0.730	Qualified
Service	5	0.702	Qualified
Satisfaction	5	0.890	Qualified

The research finds that the scale has high reliability because the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of all independent variables is greater than 0.6. Besides, the smallest Corrected item-total correlation of the variables is greater than 0.4. In addition, the Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted is greater than 0.6, the research concludes that the scales have good reliability. However, to make the above statement more accurate, the author conducted exploratory factor analysis (EFA). There are quite a few tables in the output, all of which contribute to the evaluation of the EFA analysis results as good or bad. However, here the research focuses on three main results tables: KMO and Bartlett's Test, Total Variance Explained and Rotated Component Matrix, because by using these three tables we can evaluate the appropriate EFA analysis results.

Table 3 KMO and Bartlett's Test of independent variables

KMO		.842
Bartlett	Chi-square	3541.276
	(df)	300
	Sig (P-value)	.000

KMO coefficient = 0.842 > 0.5 means that the correlation between the observed variables is large enough to conduct factor analysis. Sig (P-value) = 0.000 < 0.005, showing that the extracted factors are appropriate, so that the observed variables are correlated with each other. Thus, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is appropriate.

Table 4 Factor loading of independent variables

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
FC1	0.672				
FC2	0.608				
FC3	0.543				
FC4	0.622				
FC5	0.624				
FQ1		0.808			
FQ2		0.681			
FQ3		0.706			
FQ4		0.695			
FQ5		0.665			
HE1			0.782		
HE2			0.801		
HE3			0.747		
HE4			0.829		
HE5			0.801		
ST1				0.749	
ST2				0.718	
ST3				0.716	
ST4				0.677	
ST5				0.772	
SV1					0.507
SV2					0.574
SV3					0.547
SV4					0.508
SV5					0.623

Based on the results of the evaluation of the scale by the exploratory factor analysis method EFA and the reliability coefficient Cronbach's alpha, the formal theoretical research model adjusts 5 factors affecting customer satisfaction when using the product. The model has 6 factors, including 5 independent factors facilities, food quality, hygiene, staff, and service and 1 dependent factor satisfaction. Test the assumption of variance of error: Assume a linear relationship and the variance of the error is constant. If the assumption of a linear relationship and equal variance is satisfied, then there is no relationship between the predicted values and

the error. Linear regression analysis was performed with 5 independent variables which are facilities, food quality, hygiene issues, staff, and service and 1 dependent variable is satisfaction.

The multivariable linear regression has the form: $SF = B_0 + B_1*FC + B_2*FQ + B_3*HE + B_4*ST + B_5*SV + e_i$

Table 5 Evaluate model fit

Model	R	R ²	Standard deviation	F	1	2	Durbin Watson
1	.824	.679	.57103248	124.592	5	294	.917

The results of the model analysis have a correlation coefficient $R = 0.824 > 0.7$, so the research model is suitable to be used to evaluate the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. The model has an adjusted coefficient of $R^2 = 0.679$, which explains 67.9% of the variation in satisfaction which is explained by the variation of the independent variables. In other words, 67.9% of customer satisfaction when using the service

Table 6 Anova

Model		Sum of squares	Df	F	Level of sig	Sig.
1	Regression	203.133	5	124.592	40.627	.000
	Residual	95.867	294		.326	
	total	299.000	299			

Sig value = 0 < significance level < 0.05, reject hypothesis H0. It means that the combination of the independent variables present in the model can explain the variation of the dependent variable. Therefore, the linear model is built to fit the existing data.

Model	Un normalized coefficients		Normalization coefficient	T	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Standard error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
Constant	-1.034	.033			1.000	1.000	1.000
FC	.734	.033	.734	22.231	.000	1.000	1.000
FQ	.097	.033	.097	2.924	.004	1.000	1.000
HE	.309	.033	.309	9.353	.000	1.000	1.000
ST	.180	.033	.180	5.441	.000	1.000	1.000
SV	.058	.033	.058	1.759	.080	1.000	1.000

The above model has the exaggeration coefficient of variance of the independent variables $VIF < 2$ ($VIF = 1$) and the Tolerance coefficient both greater than 0.5 (Tolerance = 1), so the model does not violate the phenomenon of multicollinearity. The Sig values of the independent variables are all less than 0.05, showing that the test significance level between the independent

variables and the dependent variable is satisfied. The beta coefficients of the independent variables are all positive, showing that these variables have a positive relationship with the dependent variable.

From the table of results above, we get the linear regression function: $SF = -1.034 + 0.734*CSV C + 0.097*CLMA + 0.309*VDVS + 0.180*DNNV + 0.058*CPV + e_i$.

E. RECOMMENDATION

Strengthening the quality management of the banquet department is necessary. Conference service is also part of the hospitality industry. Depending on the different types of parties, their menus are also different. For conference parties, mainly finger food dishes, very simple but very influential on customer psychology. From there, it is necessary to carefully monitor the quality, service skills, quality of dishes, drinks, hygiene, and quality of serving utensils, In the process of strengthening quality management, in addition to base on criteria and quality management processes, departmental managers learn more information about the evaluation and quality management of the products. Other large banquet service enterprises or foreign organizations will understand many different quality management tasks. From there, it is possible to find out what is lacking in their quality management and find out the directions for developing the quality of party service that is suitable for the needs of customers. Most of the temporary employees are students of universities and colleges. The association with schools that teach food and beverage specialties will help the center reduce training costs and have a workforce with good service skills because students are all well-trained at the school. In addition, this is also an opportunity for the department to select official employees for the department in the future with the aim of rejuvenating human resources. The quality of equipment not only greatly affects the customer's perception of the center, but also greatly affects the service process of the staff. If the equipment and facilities are good, it will help employees work effectively and ensure labor safety. Therefore, when conditions permit, customers always want their service equipment to be of better quality, and more modern, so perfecting the quality of service equipment is an indispensable job.

F. CONCLUSION

Research results provide the concept of service quality and related concepts. The research results also provide information on the current situation and provide a model affecting the quality of the center's banquet service. The analysis results will help the topic find the factors affecting the translation quality. Through Cronbach's Alpha assessment and EFA analysis, linear regression identifies the theoretical model of factors affecting customer satisfaction when using services. The study points out the advantages and disadvantages in the most general way. Then, suggest some solutions to improve service quality

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

None

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